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e-mail: a.p.bolotnikova@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0003-4781-7475**From Mediation to Mentoring: Semantic Evolution of the Lexeme Librarian.
Based on Materials from the General Regional Annotated Corpus (GRAC)**

Objective. The purpose of the article is to comprehensively analyze the semantic transformations of the lexeme librarian, the features of its interpretation in both the lexical register and discourse. The study of theoretical material and source base made it possible to build and compare lexical-semantic fields of lexemes librarian / teacher, to show their semantic intersections - a linguistic reflection of the idea of a librarian transformed in the minds of speakers and interpreted under the influence of essential objective / subjective intra- and extralingual factors.

Methods. To achieve the defined goal, general scientific and linguistic research methods were applied. First of all, to study and explain the structure, content, and logic of dictionary definitions of the considered concept, the method of semantic analysis of definitions was used. The corpus approach made it possible to trace the frequency and dynamics of the use of lexemes librarian and teacher in discursive content. Semantic-distributive analysis made it possible to analyze the specificity and variation of the contextual compatibility of the considered lexeme, to construct a lexical-semantic field. **Results.** The results illustrate the emergence of new semiotics, layered and usual, and therefore semantic modifications caused by extralinguistic factors. **Conclusions.** The results of the study convince that the understanding of the concept of a librarian is shifting from mediation in the "information – reader" paradigm to mentoring, supervision, tutoring, teaching, and active involvement in the organization of the cultural and educational process.

Keywords: corpus-based approach; linguistic corpus; association experiment; association area; language awareness; librarian; teacher

Introduction

The discourse reflects confirmation of the intensification of the importance of the library and the development of librarianship as a significant component of the modern globalized social continuum, a significantly modified lifestyle with all its attributes, changes in the general vectors of direction of the multi-sectoral policy of Ukraine and the world society. Domestic library institutions play a significant role in the process of accumulation, storage, empowerment and dissemination of information considered one of the core values of society. This concerns the paramount importance of free and open access for every Ukrainian to reliable and time-tested information resources.

At the same time, the updated library, different from the traditional book collection, is gradually turning into a universal system that is able to meet user requests due to the ability to use the traditional reference and bibliographic apparatus, thematic information base, organized book collections, modern computer technologies, a capacious corpus of illustrative material, documents, archival data, etc. The rapid modernization of the library environment is confirmed by the extensive paradigm of the latest digital technologies, electronic information resources, modernized network service channels, implemented into the usual model of functioning of domestic libraries

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in the context of changes in the dominant vectors of their development and the transformation of methods of obtaining information – offline and online in 24/7 mode. In addition to the aforementioned, the space of modern libraries is becoming an open platform, a place for socialization of readers, a location for creative events, various formats of regional and national scale.

The change in the prevailing philosophy of library activities is causing tectonic shifts in the work of librarians, whose roles and functions are noticeably shifting: from now on, library workers not only staff, organize, and certify existing collections of printed periodicals and non-periodicals or provide information services to users. They skillfully create, support, and administer electronic databases that are constantly updated, implement remote services, adapting them to the modern information space, initiate various events and courses, transforming traditional premises with books into cultural, artistic, and educational hubs that bring users together.

All the noted extralinguistic factors expand the boundaries of the traditional interpretation of the lexeme *librarian* at the linguistic level, the key semantic transformations of which are investigated in the proposed work. The scientific research is focused on the reflection of the phenomenon *librarian* in the dictionary thesaurus and in modern discourse – linguistic corpora – with a projection onto possible semantic transformations of the “living” meaning of the lexeme under consideration and point intersections at the semantic level with the lexeme *teacher*.

The purpose of the article is to comprehensively analyze the semantic transformations of the lexeme *librarian*, the features of its interpretation in the dictionary register and discourse. To achieve the set goal, the following tasks were outlined: 1) to clarify the codified meaning of the lexeme *librarian*, identify and describe the spectrum of explicated semes; 2) to distinguish and analyze additional semes of the considered lexeme, manifested in the discursive field; 3) to build on the GRAC-18 corpus and compare the lexical-semantic fields of the lexemes *librarian* / *teacher*, and show their semantic intersections.

The results of this study contribute to a broader understanding of how speakers perceive the concept under consideration. This research also helps to systematize its documented uses in both the dictionary thesaurus and broader discourse. These points underscore the relevance and urgency of the proposed study in the context of general multi-format transformations and the modernization of fields directly or indirectly related to the library and its professionals.

Methods

In this study, the focus is on comparing the codified meaning of the phenomenon *librarian*, in particular, the one that is presented in the dictionary register with the one recorded in the minds of speakers and interpreted depending on a number of objective / subjective intra- and extralingual factors. The discursive meaning is analyzed using materials presented in the General Regional Annotated Corpus (GRAC) (<https://uacorporus.org/>). The priority is to build and analyze the contextual compatibility of the considered stimulus *librarian* and its semantic intersections with the lexeme *teacher*, considering the projections of the subjective worldview of the producers of the discourse.

The selected research methods are subordinated to the achievement of the set goal: the work uses general scientific methods of *observation*, *comparison*, *generalization*, *description* and *systematization* - at the stage of selection, analysis and inventory of factual material; linguistic methods themselves, in particular the method of *linguistic observation*, *description*, *distribution*, are used to interpret and systematize collocations presented in the discourse. To study and clarify the structure, content, logic of dictionary definitions of the studied concept, the method of *semantic analysis* of definitions was used.

The corpus approach made it possible to trace the frequency and dynamics of the use of both lexemes, *librarian* and *teacher*, in artistic and journalistic discourses, to analyze the specifics and variations of its contextual compatibility, to build their lexical and semantic fields.

Results and Discussion

Current issues of development and transformation of domestic libraries, their compliance with declared international standards, theoretical foundations and practical implementation of strategies for modernization of the library sector are generally presented in scientific research by many Ukrainian scholars (V. Bilous, M. Demidko, T. Kolesnykova, O. Klymenko, L. Konoval, K. Lobuzina, T. Opryshko, N. Pasmor, O. Sokur, P. Skladanyi, T. Chorna, M. Shevchenko, V. Shevchuk, T. Yaroshenko, et al).

The academic literature emphasizes the change in the traditional vision of the library, the expansion of its functions and key vectors of activity. A number of works are devoted not only to the consideration of trends and possible problems of modifying the traditional library sphere in accordance with the demands of today, but also to the modern specifics of the work of its employees, shifts in the traditional model of interaction between *librarian* and *reader*. As a confirmation of this, “In today's information society, the role of librarians is undergoing significant transformations. From traditional providers of information, they are gradually turning into teachers and mentors who help researchers navigate the complex world of modern science” (Opryshko, 2024). Researchers are convinced of the gradual adaptation of the librarian to the demands of the multimodal space: “Librarians of scientific libraries provide consultations, training and support in: publishing; open access and promotion of publications; initiatives in the field of digital scientific publishing; complex ecosystem of scientific communication” (Lobuzina, Harahulia, Konoval, & Lobuzin, 2020). Similar considerations are found in the scientific work of N. Pasmor, M. Shevchenko, and J. Pasmor (2024): “However, in this case, researchers also point to an obvious change in the traditional perception of the modern university library through the transformation of its functions and information image, emphasizing the strengthening of communication interaction during remote work in wartime”.

As can be seen, the spectrum of responsibilities of modern librarians partly contrasts with the traditional and time-tested ones. According to researchers, “A modern librarian is a psychologist, an actor, a director, an expert in modern computer technologies, and, most importantly, a true friend and advisor to the user” (Kolesnykova, Gorbova, & Shcherbatiuk, 2022). Reflecting on the involvement of a librarian in the educational process, T. Kolesnykova and her colleagues add: “They organize leisure practices aimed at understanding and actively adopting the values of the democratic world by Ukrainian students, where an important condition for successful development is the conscious and active participation of citizens in public life, openness of knowledge, barrier-free access, tolerance and patriotism” (Kolesnykova, Gorbova, & Shcherbatiuk, 2022).

If initially, according to most scientists, the understanding of the concept of *librarian* focused only on mediation – an information carrier that, in one symbolic form or another, provides a connection between the source (book) and its reader, then later, with the development of technology, it expanded and began to include a pedagogical component, which became a necessary condition for the activities of a modern librarian.

In addition, it is worth to mention the strengthening and diversification of the usual roles of librarians – in the context of transformations within the very system of functioning of the domestic library industry, they are perceived not only as translators of existing information content or intermediaries in working with books and other sources of information. Modern librarians are

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seen as mentors, creative coaches, organizers and educators: “Modern librarians are not guardians of book collections – they act as strategic partners in research and educational activities, providing access to world information resources and creating their own” (Chorna, 2025).

The librarian’s ability to interact with the reader is extremely important. New generation specialists must not only professionally master new library and information technologies, but also have knowledge in the pedagogical and psychological field: “A librarian must be able to establish contact with the audience, know its socio-psychological features in depth and in detail, and systematically study the effectiveness of what has been done” (Shevchuk, 2018). Not the least role in this process is played by professional growth, constant professional development, communication with colleagues with the aim of learning new things, and spreading best practices in managing the field of book studies and library studies in general: “The qualification of a modern librarian fully depends on his or her abilities, level of general and professional education, degree of theoretical training, and ability to adapt to the urgent requirements of the constantly changing times” (Sokur & Klymenko, 2024).

Extralinguistic reality provides the impetus and material for a multifaceted linguistic study of how changes are reflected in language. Along with a partial renewal of the thesaurus (librarian-mentor, librarian-teacher, librarian-organizer, librarian-curator, freelance librarian, librarian-trainer, web librarian, leader librarian, etc.), the combinatory potential of the lexeme *librarian* has been significantly expanded.

The appearance of collocations like *mobile librarian*, *creative librarian*, *highly qualified librarian*, *advisor in the library*, *librarian as a mediator*, *librarian of the year*, *librarian organizes*, *librarian teaches*, *a librarian’s presentation*, *a librarian’s portfolio*, and *a forum of librarians*, etc. points to a semantic reinterpretation of the entire phenomenon of the *librarian*. Such and similar linguistic reflections confirm the modernization of the lexeme *librarian*, its semantic changes, and its adaptation to current domestic and global shifts in all spheres of life, particularly in the fields related to culture and educational activity.

The aforementioned modifications at the semantic level once again convince us of the irrationality of considering a word outside of context, that is, as it is codified in dictionary registers. Of course, discursive contexts do not always correlate with the usual options given in lexicographic sources: a holistic, vivid reflection of the picture of the current linguistic space without taking into account the features of modern word usage and possible changes in its meaning is violated.

It is well known that the word *librarian* comes from the word *library*, interpreted in the dictionary register as “1. An institution, a cultural and educational institution where books, magazines, etc. are stored and issued to readers, and where literary works are promoted and disseminated. 2. A more or less significant number of books specially selected for reading, scientific work, for the purpose of collecting, etc. 3. A room, a room for storing books; a book depository. 4. The name of serial publications or books or magazines related in theme, intended for a certain category of readers” (Bilodid, Horetskyi, Buriachok, Hnatiuk, & Shvydka, 1970).

However, as contemporary scholars rightly point out, “When actualized in the minds of modern speakers, particularly the younger generation, the lexeme *library* is increasingly associated with a diverse hub that contains a complex of various types of information in traditional and modern formats” (Zhovnir & Leshchenko, 2024). There is little surprise or opposition to the argument that “The modern paradigm of library services is based not only on the use of a specific library’s document collection, but also on the use of fundamentally new opportunities for information access regardless of the time and location of either the document or the user” (Zhukova, 2024). The librarian is becoming an active participant in satisfying the educational, informational, and cultural needs of library users by providing access not only to documented

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knowledge and information stored in its collections but also in real and virtual spaces. It is more correct to position the librarian at the center of the educational discourse within the “educational institution – library” paradigm.

Traditionally, in official lexicographic sources, the lexeme *librarian* is recorded with the meaning “Library employee, library specialist” (Bilodid, Horetskyi, Buriachok, Hnatiuk, & Shvydka, 1970). There is also an interpretation of the term *bookseller* from a more obsolete linguistic stratum: “1. Book trade employee. 2. Obsolete: Bookstore owner. 3. Obsolete: Librarian”. It is noteworthy that in the dictionary of the Old Ukrainian language of the XIV–XV centuries (Hrynchyshyn, Humetska, & Kernytskyi, 1977) the nomination *librarian* is not recorded, there are no interpretations and no derivatives of it. B. Hrinchenko does not record the studied lexeme in his “Dictionary of the Ukrainian language”. The dynamics of fixation of the lexeme *librarian* is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Dynamics of fixation of the lexeme *librarian* in the dictionary register

Dictionary name	Year of publication	Absence / presence of definition
DUL-11	1973	+
DUL-20	1917	+
“Dictionary of the Ukrainian Language” B. Hrinchenko	1959 (reprint edition of 1909)	–
Dictionary of the Old Ukrainian Language of the XIV-XV Centuries.	1977-1978	–
Etymological dictionary of the Ukrainian language	1982–2006	+

The considered definitions expound a number of relevant characteristics of a librarian, in particular his or her professional employment directly related to working with books, user service, awareness of the formation of library funds and mediation between the reader and the printed product, and therefore the positioning of the librarian as a key component of the effectiveness of the traditional information and library sphere.

Including the linguistic plane in the consideration, it is noted that the lexemes *teacher* and *librarian* in modern discourse function in parallel: the teaching and educational activities of the teacher are combined with the supervision, administration, mentoring and tutoring of the librarian-innovator. As for the dictionary register, the nomination *teacher* is codified with the meaning “a person who conducts teaching and educational work or develops issues related to pedagogy” (Bilodid, Lahutina, & Lenets, 1975). Despite the fact that the cultural, educational and outreach segments in Ukraine have been formed for a long time, the lexeme under consideration is not represented in previously published thesauri, specifically the Dictionary of the Old Ukrainian Language of the XIV–XV Centuries and the Dictionary of the Ukrainian Language.

The usual codified interpretations specify only sporadic semantic intersections of the studied nominations – *librarian* / *teacher*. The usual perception of a teacher in the midst of the educational process contrasts with the positioning of a librarian as a person responsible for the storage, book products registration, and its further popularization among readers.

Without denying that the key fixer of any information and discursive speech is the text, it is advisable to note that the meanings expressed in the dictionary register are considered the primary meaning of a term or concept, separated from any connotative colorings or semantic strata.

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Only the context can fully reveal its semantic content, which allows to reveal the updated deep meanings that the denotatum acquired in the process of conceptualizing reality. The involvement of variations in the modern use of the word with the existing linguistic imprints of extralingual processes makes it possible to fix the connotative, axiological, stylistic plans of meaning and essential semantic shifts.

The on-demand reality convinces that librarians are gradually taking on the role of teachers-organizers, lecturers, speakers at various events, sometimes initiating and coordinating their implementation. They are increasingly mentors, tutors in the operational search for literature and sources of scientific information, maintaining author profiles, scientometrics, academic integrity, etc. All of the above once again prompts thoughts about shifts in the semantics of lexemes, and this mainly concerns the correction of vectors of pragmatic meaning: librarians play the role of teachers, which does not contradict, but rather illustrates the key trends in the development of the domestic library industry.

It is natural that modern discourse contains both the lexemes considered in the investigation, both *librarian* and *teacher*. To strengthen the fixation of possible semantic variations and changes that occur under the influence of obvious and partially outlined extralinguistic factors, an appeal is made to language corpora, which can be interpreted as a kind of text and discourse banks. For this investigation, the data presented in the 18th General Regional Annotated Corpus (GRAC-18) was selected. This choice was due to the significant number of tokens presented in it (the total number of word forms identified in the corpus is presented in Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Frequency distribution of the lexeme *librarian* in the General Regional Annotated Corpus (GRAC-18)

In the General Regional Annotated Corpus (GRAC-18), the lexeme considered in the study is represented by a significant number of tokens (word forms) – 1197. As a result of the **CQL query [lemma="librarian"]**, 4,805 (2.64 per million) of its representation options were obtained (Fig. 2)

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Fig. 2. Frequency distribution of the lexeme *librarian*

To illustrate the frequency of combinations of a particular lexical unit with other words, that is, its established contextual phenomena, within the corpus approach, collocation analysis is used. *Collocation* is repeated syntagmatic combinations of words. Researchers are still debating the essence of this concept: definitions vary depending on the approach taken as a basis during interpretation, namely context-oriented, semantic-syntactic, corpus or corpus-statistical.

Without delving into the theoretical plane of the issue, let us only note in passing that in the linguistic space there is a view of *collocations* as complex semantic-syntactic units, which are characterized by semantic, syntactic and distributive regularity, that is, a typical and fixed verbal environment. Such an interpretation was proposed in the vein of the ideas of British contextualism and is associated with the name of J. R. Firth (Firth, 1957, pp. 190-215). Collocation is one of the main concepts of S. Evert's research "The Statistics of Word Cooccurrences: Word Pairs and Collocations". According to the researcher, "A collocation is a word combination whose semantic and/or syntactic properties cannot be fully predicted from those of its components, and therefore which should be listed in the lexicon" (Evert, 2005). However, the author notes on occasion that "The precise interpretation of the definition depends on the properties under consideration (e.g., semantic compositionality versus syntactic modifiability), on the processes involved in 'predicting' the properties of the combination (e.g., composition of literal meanings versus metaphorical interpretation), and on the form and intended use of the lexicon (which can range from a syntactic partner's word list to the human mental lexicon in psycholinguistic studies)" (Evert, 2005).

In the domestic linguistic tradition, the understanding of *collocation* is poorly researched and is at the stage of being formalized. In particular, T. Bobkova argues that the concept used in studies based on the corpus approach is interpreted by scientists in a narrow sense as a sequence of words that often occur in the text, outlining collocation as a "continuum between free and stable compounds" (Bobkova, 2014). In the works of N. Lototska, another vision of the phenomenon under consideration is proposed: "collocations are language units that are widespread in the lexical-semantic system, which are used according to the strict rules of combinatorics and realize their potential in the process of forming language constructions" (Lototska, 2019). The interpretation presented in the scientific works of R.-Yu. Perkhach and S. Karpa is impressive. In their opinion, "A collocation is a combination of two words that are habitually and frequently used together, one of which is more prominent and dominant compared to another word that joins it in order to delimit its meaning" (Perkhach & Karpa, 2023). The authors include in the consideration the linguistic plane and tools for detecting and analyzing collocations.

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In this research, *collocations* are qualified as specific word combinations, frequent occurrences of words that are used together in a text more often than separately by chance. The analysis of collocations makes it possible to build a system of stable linguistic connections – representatives of established ideas about concepts, fixed in the human mind and interpreted by it in the context of a particular linguistic picture of the world.

A search of the GRAC-18 corpus using the **CQL1 query [lemma="librarian"]** revealed 4805 occurrences. The most commonly used contextual phenomena were: *reading* (MI=11.65;logDice=6.29), *leading* (MI=8.29;logDice=4.68), *school* (MI=7.65;logDice=4.03), *university* (MI=7.07;logDice=3.18), *centralized* (MI=6.08;logDice=2.27), *district* (MI=4.15;logDice=0.39), *scientific* (MI=4.47;logDice=1.20), *professional* (MI=4.08;logDice=0.5), *respected* (MI=3.23;logDice=-0.32); *teach* (MI=5.26;logDice=1.27), *work* (MI=8.01;logDice=3.85), (MI=5.46;logDice=1.48), *tell* (MI=5.03;logDice=1.47), *organize* (MI=5.69;logDice=1.98), *choose* (MI=4.55;logDice=0.91), *prepare* (MI=5.05;logDice=1.43), *conduct* (MI=3.11;logDice=-0.43), *help* (MI=2.85;logDice=-0.70); *branch library* (MI=12.19;logDice=5.42), *book collection* (MI=10.16;logDice=4.42), *subscription* (MI=8.67;logDice=3.94), *reading room* (MI=8.15;logDice=3.48), *seminar* (MI=6.45;logDice=2.23), *library* (MI=5.14;logDice=1.53), *club* (MI=5.21;logDice=1.47), *reader* (MI=4.24;logDice=0.65), *duty* (MI=4.39;logDice=0.82), *meeting* (MI=4.93;logDice=1.22), *department* (MI=5.46;logDice=2.20), *conference* (MI=3.85;logDice=0.25), *forum* (MI=3.72;logDice=0.11) etc. The contextual potential of the considered lexeme is expanded by combining it with service parts of speech, which, despite their frequency, were not taken into consideration due to their semantic low informativeness.

A search for the **CQL1 query [lemma="teacher"]** revealed 28,178 occurrences in the corpus. Analysis of the conjugation of the lexeme teacher in a linear flow in the corpus confirmed the partial linguistic diversity of contextual ties: the activity of conjugation with adjectives, nouns, and verbs was recorded. Here is an example of a sample of frequent expressions with the MI / logDice indicators: *experienced* (MI=9.02;logDice=7.19), *highly qualified* (MI=7.59;logDice=5.51), *prominent* (MI=6.74;logDice=4.58), *famous* (MI=5.99;logDice=4.48), *knowledgeable* (MI=9.04;logDice=3.64), *talented* (MI=8.39;logDice=6.56), *authoritative* (MI=5.40;logDice=3.18), *genuine* (MI=4.09;logDice=2.96); *rural* (MI=4.00;logDice=2.85); *future* (MI=5.61;logDice=2.37), *knowledgeable* (MI=5.89;logDice=2.33), *qualified* (MI=5.59;logDice=5.51), *professional* (MI=5.63;logDice=3.42); *professional* (MI=4.63;logDice=3.41); *competent* (MI=4.97;logDice=2.55); *leading* (MI=4.32;logDice=1.06), *highly professional* (MI=7.32;logDice=2.44); *creative* (MI=3.78;logDice=2.48), *good* (MI=3.56;logDice=2.41); *teach* (MI=7.87;logDice=5.97); *Ukrainian* (MI=3.23;logDice=2.24); *advise* (MI=4.73;logDice=3.18); *prepare* (MI=3.81;logDice=2.56); *instruct* (MI=7.01;logDice=3.59), *think* (MI=9.71;logDice=3.76), *nominate* (MI=8.98;logDice=4.17), *lecture* (MI=6.23;logDice=2.80), *reward* (MI=5.61;logDice=2.18), *interest* (MI=5.66;logDice=2.16), *work* (MI=4.41;logDice=1.24), *tell* (MI=logDice=0.11); *constellation* (MI=9.67;logDice=4.85), *achievements* (MI=7.25;logDice=3.23), *book* (MI=2.40;logDice=-0.81), *legacy* (MI=6.45;logDice=3.15), *workshop* (MI=6.70;logDice=3.61), *student* (MI=6.73;logDice=2.92), *competence* (MI=6.63;logDice=2.85), *experience* (MI=10.24;logDice=0.39), *work* (MI=12.81;logDice=0.71), *competence* (MI=6.61;logDice=2.85).

As a result of sorting the frequency of the lexemes *librarian* / *teacher* by the T-score criterion, the most frequent combination with a comma was revealed.

As it can be seen from the obtained results, collocations tend to the direct nominative meanings of the words *librarian* / *teacher*, which are as close as possible to their dictionary

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interpretations. At the same time, the results of the analysis of discursive fragments of the GRAC-18 corpus demonstrate the relevance of the argument about the denotative scale of the representation of a phenomenon or phenomenon in the images of consciousness of speakers of a certain language compared to their dictionary interpretations. The semantic fields of both overlap and are significantly wider than those recorded in dictionaries.

Librarian in discourse is a highly qualified and experienced employee of the library industry, whose work is closely related to educational activities. The inherent features of librarians – professionalism, qualification, experience – are explicated at the linguistic level by the corresponding tokens used to indicate the assessment of suitability for performing a certain job, such as: *leading, qualified, highly qualified, advanced, professional, specialist*, etc. The change in traditional professional vectors is represented by the nomens *to tell, conduct, organize, teach, manage, explain, help, conference, forum, speech, science*, etc. All the tokens presented above confirm the expansion of the circle of usual and time-tested professional duties of a librarian, mainly due to his or her active involvement in various formats of activities aimed at training and education.

The vision of the *teacher* is formed in the minds of Ukrainians by a complex of semantically variegated collocations, but such that do not contradict its lexicographic interpretation. Although the structure of the nuclei and centers of meanings of the collocations *librarian* and *teacher* is different, semantic intersections are fixed. In the nucleus of both lexemes *to be* – 108 and 518 occurrences, respectively (the number of occurrences changes when choosing a search that contains word forms). It is likely that collocations - predicative nuclei prevail: “*The full list of speakers and the program here for those who are **teachers**, psychologists, social workers by profession - this is simply a necessary event from the point of view of professional development, because this is where the fair of advanced technologies in psychology, coaching, art techniques, etc. is held*”, “*Experts who are public figures, about whom it is easy to find on the Internet, are involved in the evaluation process, to be sure of their competence there are **librarians** who work with people on the ground and know what ‘comes’ to readers*” (GRAC-18).

Attribute distributions are described by the model “**adjective + librarian**”, which is implemented in the CQL query [tag=“adj.*”&tag!=“.*pron.*”][lemma=“librarian”]. Such a search reveals 429 contexts, which confirms the active use of the lexeme by discourse producers. To avoid chaotic description, contexts with attributive lemmas are ranked according to the lexical-semantic criterion into several groups: 1) nomens to indicate the specifics of labor activity (*senior, junior, leading, regular, gymnasium, former, main, private, on duty, former, employed, new, appointed, electronic*, etc.); 2) nomens to indicate the location of labor activity (*rural, urban, Ukrainian, Polish, Chernihiv, Nizhyn, New Zealand, American, Czech, Donetsk, Cherkasy, Carpathian*, etc.); 3) nomens to indicate appearance (*plump, middle-aged, young, youthful, quite tall, tall, corpulent, elderly, beautiful, red-haired*, etc.); 4) nomenclature to denote professional characteristics (*modern, expert, professional, innate, best, good, leading, excellent, high-quality, scholarly, genuine, not bad, most modern, friendly, modest, outstanding, enlightened*, etc.).

It is noticeable that the lexeme *librarian* is actualized in the minds of speakers with positive and negative connotations. Positively marked variants prevail – *patient, kind, hardworking, wonderful, friendly, caring*, etc. Among the recorded variants of negative connotation – *annoying, evil, caricature, wicked, vile, harsh, arrogant, bad, pompous*, etc. Both contexts coexist in the same discursive plane, they should not be opposed, logically considered not separately, but together.

The CQL query [tag=“adj.*”&tag!=“.*pron.*”][lemma=“teacher”] yielded contexts with 6192 attribute lemmas indicating: professional qualities of the teacher (*professional, qualified, highly qualified, graduated, outstanding, brilliant, progressive, famous, talented*,

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recognized, beautiful, experienced, best, knowledgeable, leading, selfless, brilliant, bright, chic, stunning, etc.), personal qualities of the teacher (*educated, wise, gifted, sensitive, brave, cheerful, demanding, quiet, sensual, etc.*), local affiliation (*urban, rural, Ukrainian, Polish, British, American, Chernihiv, Khmelnytskyi, Rivne, etc.*), specifics of pedagogical activity (*correctional, social, main, musical, folk, school, museum, elite, accompanying, etc.*). Contrasting to the vast majority of attributes with positive coloring found in the corpus are fixations of negatively marked semantics, for example, *hardened, tough, nervous, nasty, bad*). The unitary possibilities of the specified verbal unit under consideration are expanded: from rural / urban teachers in older periods, to progressive and highly qualified, who have significant functional and pragmatic weight nowadays.

The presented sample represents the point intersections of both lexical units, *librarian / teacher*, at the semantic level: a librarian, like a teacher, must be a highly qualified specialist, an exemplary specialist, capable of self-development, self-study, advanced training and acquisition of new professional experience for further transmission of knowledge to readers. Dedication, creativity, inner talent and a desire to learn contribute to the disclosure of the potential of a librarian in the formation of reading competence, instilling thoughtful reading and an attitude towards printed products in general, and therefore pedagogical adjustment of reading needs, tolerance of presented ideas, thoughts, mental and behavioral stereotypes.

Verbative distributions describe the models “**librarian+verb**” / “**teacher+verb**”, which are implemented in the CQL1 query [lemma=“librarian”][tag=“verb.*”] / [lemma=“teacher”][tag=“verb.*”]. The first query yielded a concordance of 725 contexts (frequency 0.4 per 1 million), the second – 3805 with a frequency of 2.09 per million tokens. Both tokens in the considered corpora are presented in combination with verbs of different semantics. For example, analysis reveals frequent contextual occurrences of the lexeme *librarian* with the verbalisms *to come, emphasize, work, educate, collect, advise, do, learn, receive, pass, take, visit, know, ask, read, tell, plan, give, issue, be able, must, perceive, expect, etc.* At the same time, the teacher comes across the verbs *to be, educate, carry out, instill, speak, teach, work, convince, must, engage, bring, understand, write, give, keep, influence, contact, choose, appreciate, ask, become, sign, etc.*

The idea that a modern librarian performs the functions of education, reading and spiritual development of users, contributes to the upbringing of culture, the formation and development of reading competence, as well as subject-subject interaction in the process of library service is actively represented in the discourse by the verbs to conduct, organize, speak, provide, tell, teach, present, respond, report, read, invite, involve, instill, expand, etc.: “*At the end of the lesson, the librarian conducted a literary game ‘Try – guess’ with the students, and the children viewed the book exhibition “In the world of the amazing, interesting, fascinating”, “Librarians invite daredevils to pleasant meetings with book novelties in the city’s libraries”, “Biblio-hub on A. Sheptytskyi Street, where an ordinary library was turned into an institution for cultural leisure for everyone: special computer programs for people with visual impairments; meetings with writers; free courses and workshops for everyone; lectures on various issues (from history to law); Sunday readings for the little ones ‘The Librarian Reads to Children’.*”

Lexemes that form the cores are a projection of the collective worldview, feelings, ideas, thoughts, images of consciousness, manifested through the word. So, a librarian is perceived through the prism of evaluation (the positively colored collocation *leading*), a teacher – in the context of nationality, the specifics of professional activity, represented by the nomens *Ukrainian* and *social*. For ease of perception, examples of frequently used collocations that form the core and center of the associative field are included in Table 2.

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Table 2

Ranking of *librarian* and *teacher* collocation frequencies in discourse

Librarian	Teacher
To work – 122 (2.5%)	To be – 518 (1.8%)
To be – 108 (2.3%)	Social – 471 (1.7%)
Leading – 73 (1.5%)	Ukrainian – 387 (1.4%)
Rural 50	Experienced 283
Main 45	Outstanding 279
School 40	Young 220
Big 35	To have 185
Assistant 33	School 184
Department 33	Talented 183
To become 25	Salary 178
This 25	Future 176
To tell 23	To work 174
To say 23	Work 164
Senior 23	Every 127
Ukrainian 22	Better 126
Position 22	Famous 123
Young 21	To teach 114
Scientific 19	All 108
The most 19	Great 107
Good 18	Wonderful 105
Old 18	My 103
Must 17	Our 101
Reading 16	Thousand 92
Profession 16	Best 89
Salary 15	Modern 66

The study of discourse shows that the lexeme *librarian*, as it is actualized in the minds of speakers, is associated not only with books, book exchanges, or information retrieval – the usual attributes of libraries and librarianship in general. This is evidenced by the varied collocations recorded in the sample, including different parts of speech like *book*, *book collection*, *library*, *branch*, *library-branch*, *room*, *reading*, *department*, *to read*, *to inform*, *to answer*, *to show*, *to provide*, *to offer*, *to consult*, *to collect*, *to give*, etc.

The expanding combinatory potential of the lexeme *librarian* reveals the dynamism of the extralinguistic system. The appearance of terms like *delegation*, *congress*, *exhibition*, *event*, *conference*, *science*, *smart*, *to join*, *to represent*, *to speak*, *to talk*, *to consider*, *to report*, etc in the discourse confirms librarians' increasing involvement in diverse cultural, educational, and training events. A modern librarian is fully equipped with the necessary tools to ensure free and continuous access to literature, information, and data for everyone who makes a relevant request. In addition, their interests and responsibilities include creating, organizing, and managing educational, cultural, and scientific events, utilizing modern information technologies and devices.

A librarian's pedagogical potential is reflected in lexemes such as *teach*, *educate*, *tell*, *show*, *answer (questions)*, *provide (consultations)*, *book*, *textbook*, *school*, *university*, *potential*, *science*, *learning*, *evaluation*, etc. This is a clear example of the neosemanticism process, which has

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developed under the influence of modern realities. New-generation specialists must not only master new library and information technologies but also possess knowledge of the pedagogical and psychological fields.

In public perception, the modern librarian is seen as a specialist who assists in the complex and lengthy process of developing reading competence. This includes instilling thoughtful reading skills, guiding the search and selection of necessary literature, and pedagogically adjusting reading needs—a role that cultivates exemplary qualities in library users. A librarian teaches and trains others to learn through books.

The lexical-semantic field of the lexeme *librarian*, derived from the GRAC-18 corpus, is presented below in Fig. 3.

Fig.3. Lexical-semantic field of the lexeme *librarian*

Conclusions

The meaning of a word, as presented in dictionaries, explicates the primary, denotational content of any term or concept, which is largely devoid of connotative layers. In the process of development of society and changes in extralingual realities, semantic transformations of words are recorded: modifications are reflected at all linguistic levels, primarily at the lexical-semantic level.

The results of observation of the dictionary register showed that in the considered definitions of the lexeme *librarian*, the attributes of the professional activity of the librarian as an intermediary between the reader and sources of information content are explicated, while the lexeme *teacher* is codified with an emphasis on its educational function.

Semantic-distributive analysis of the lexemes *librarian* / *teacher* made it possible to identify additional semes explicated in the discursive content, which confirm their involvement in teaching, educational and upbringing activities, as well as supervision, administration and mentoring. In public perception, modern, innovative librarians are qualified professionals with expertise in both library and information science and educational psychology.

REFERENCES

- Bilodid, I. K., Horetskyi, P. Y., Buriachok, A. A., Hnatiuk, H. M., & Shvydka, N. I. (Eds.). (1970). *Slovník ukraínskoi movy* (Vol. 1, p. 173). Kyiv, Ukraine: Naukova dumka. Retrieved from <https://irbis-nbuv.gov.ua/ulib/item/UKR0001576> (in Ukrainian)
- Bilodid, I. K., Lahutina, A. V., & Lenets K. V. (Eds.). (1975). *Slovník ukraínskoi movy* (Vol. 6). Kyiv, Ukraine: Naukova dumka. Retrieved from <https://irbis-nbuv.gov.ua/ulib/item/UKR0001576> (in Ukrainian)
- Bobkova, T. V. (2014). Teoretyko-metodolohichni pidkhody do vyvchennia kolokatsii u suchasnomu movoznavstvi. *Messenger of Kyiv National Linguistic University. Series Philology*, 17(2), 14-22. Retrieved from <http://philmessenger.knlu.edu.ua/article/view/103039> (in Ukrainian)
- Chorna, T. V. (2025). Profesiinyi rozvytok bibliotekariv: vyklyky ta perspektyvy v epokhu tsyfrovyykh transformatsii. In *Suchasna bibliotechno-informatsiina bezpererвна osvita: maibutnie tvorytsia sohodni. Proceedings of the XII International Scientific and Practical Conference* (pp. 22-25), Ukrainian Library Association. Kyiv, Ukraine. Retrieved from <https://ula.org.ua/resursy/vydannia> (in Ukrainian)
- Evert, S. (2005). *The statistics of word cooccurrences: Word pairs and collocations* [PhD dissertation, University of Stuttgart]. OPUS. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18419/opus-2556> (in English).
- Firth, J. R. (1957). *Papers in Linguistics 1934-1951*. London: Oxford University Press. (in English)
- Hrynchyshyn, D. H., Humetska, L. L., & Kernytskyi, I. M. (Eds.). (1977). *Slovník staroukraínskoi movy XIV–XV st.* (Vol. 1). Kyiv, Ukraine: Naukova dumka. Retrieved from <http://resource.history.org.ua/item/0006938> (in Ukrainian)
- Kolesnykova, T. O., Gorbova, O. V., & Shcherbatiuk, T. G. (2022). Pro dystantsiine navchannia, vidkryti osvichni resursy ta rol v tsykh protsesakh universytetskykh bibliotek [On distance learning, open educational resources, and the role of university libraries in these processes]. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 7, 66-77. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2022_271088 (in English)
- Lobuzina, K. V., Harahulia, S. S., Konoval, L. V., & Lobuzin, I. V. (2020). Biblioteka tsyfrovoho suspilstva v zabezpechenni systemnoi pidtrymky naukovykh doslidzhen [Digital society library in providing system support to science research]. *Library Science. Record Studies. Informology*, 4, 5-12. doi: <https://doi.org/10.32461/2409-9805.4.2020.227040> (in Ukrainian)
- Lototska, N. Ya. (2019). Doslidzhennia kolokatsii u suchasnomu movoznavstvi: korpusno-statystychnyi pidkhid [Collocation research in modern linguistics: Corpus and statistical approaches]. *Current Issues of Linguistics and Translation Studies*, 16, 122-126. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/apftp_2019_16_27 (in Ukrainian)
- Opryshko, T. S. (2024). New roles of a librarian: The experience of Grinchenko University. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 9, 237-241. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2024_316705 (in English)
- Pasmor, N. P., Shevchenko, M. O., & Pasmor, J. V. (2024). Changes in the activities of the library of the Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University in the framework of open science. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 9, 107-113. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2024_315082 (in English)
- Perkhach R.-Yu. T., & Karpa S. R. (2023). Vykorystannia instrumentariiu Sketch Engine dlia vyivlennia kolokatsii. [Using the Sketch Engine toolkit to detect collocations]. *Young Scientist*, 11(123), 49-52. doi: <https://doi.org/10.32839/2304-5809/2023-11-123-30> (in Ukrainian)
- Shevchuk, V. A. (2018). Suchasna biblioteka. Udoskonalenyi bibliotekar – zadovolenyi korystuvach. *Naukovi pratsi Kam'ianets-Podilskoho natsionalnoho universytetu imeni*

CHANGING ROLES: FROM INFORMATION PROVIDERS TO EDUCATORS

- Ivana Ohiiienka. Serii: Bibliotekoznavstvo Knyhoznnavstvo, 5, 197-200. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/npkpnuiobk_2018_5_38 (in Ukrainian)*
- Sokur, O., & Klymenko, O. (2024). Stanovlennia systemy pidvyshchennia kvalifikatsii bibliotekariv u Natsionalnii bibliotetsi Ukrainy imeni V. I. Vernadskoho [Formation of the system of professional development of librarians in the V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of UKRAINE]. *Bibliotechnyi visnyk*, 3, 64-78. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15407/bv2024.03.064> (in Ukrainian)
- Zhovnir, M. M., & Leshchenko, T. O. (2024). Library in the language consciousness of modern students: from a book depository to a cultural and educational hub (based on a free associative experiment). *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 9, 204-216. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2024_313581 (in English)
- Zhukova, A. R. (2024). The role and place of the library as an information centre in the process of learning foreign languages. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, 9, 217-225. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2024_316966 (in English)

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Від посередництва до наставництва: семантична еволюція лексеми «бібліотекар». На матеріалах Генерального регіонального анотованого корпусу (ГРАК)

Мета пропонованої статті – цілісно проаналізувати значеннєві трансформації лексеми «бібліотекар», особливості її інтерпретації у словниковому реєстрі й дискурсі. Опрацювання теоретичного матеріалу та джерельної бази дало змогу вибудувати й зіставити лексико-семантичні поля лексем «бібліотекар» / «педагог», показати їхні значеннєві перетини – лінгвальне відображення трансформованого у свідомості мовців та інтерпретованого під впливом присутніх об'єктивних / суб'єктивних інтра- й екстралінгвальних чинників уявлення про бібліотекаря. **Методика.** Для досягнення окресленої мети було застосовано загальнонаукові та лінгвістичні методи дослідження. Передовсім, для вивчення та роз'яснення структури, змісту, логіки словникових визначень досліджуваного поняття було використано метод семантичного аналізу дефініцій. Корпусний підхід дав змогу простежити частотність і динаміку вживання лексем «бібліотекар» і «педагог» у дискурсивному контенті. Семантико-дистрибутивний аналіз уможливив аналіз специфіки та варіації контекстуальної сполучуваності розглядуваної лексеми, побудову лексико-семантичного поля. **Результати** ілюструють спричинену екстремовними факторами появу нових сем, нашаровані та узуальні, а відтак – значеннєві модифікації. **Висновки.** Результати дослідження переконують в тому, що розуміння поняття «бібліотекар» зміщується від посередництва в парадигмі «інформація – читач» до наставництва, курування, тьюторства, навчання, активного долучення до організації культурно-освітнього процесу.

Ключові слова: корпусний підхід; лінгвістичний корпус; асоціативний експеримент; асоціативне поле; мовна свідомість; бібліотекар; педагог

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